

ESTIMATIVA DOS FATORES QUE AFETAM O CRESCIMENTO DE ALGAS NO LAGO DE UM EL-NAAJ USANDO TÉCNICAS DE SENSORIAMENTO REMOTO

ESTIMATION THE FACTORS AFFECTING ON GROWTH OF ALGAE IN UM EL-NAAJ LAKE BY USING REMOTE SENSING TECHNIQUES

تقدير العوامل المؤثرة على نمو الطحالب في بحيرة أم النعاج باستخدام تقنيات الاستشعار عن بعد

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RESUMO

As algas epífitas aderentes às plantas aquáticas são um elo essencial na composição da cadeia alimentar de qualquer ecossistema. As algas epífitas atuam como produtoras primárias da cadeia alimentar no ecossistema aquático e como alimento natural para o zooplâncton herbívoro e peixes. Este estudo teve como objetivo detectar a presença de colônias de algas através de sensoriamento remoto e analisar fatores que afetam o crescimento de algas por meio de levantamento de campo e interpretação visual de imagens de satélite no lago Um El-Naaj. As amostras foram coletadas em seis locais no lago Um El-Naaj no período de novembro de 2018 a junho de 2019. As amostras de algas foram coletadas de partes submersas de plantas aquáticas emergentes (macrófitas aquáticas *Phragmites australis*) e armazenadas em sacos plásticos com pouca água do ambiente e soluções para a preservação no campo e no laboratório. Amostras de água foram coletadas para estudar os fatores nutricionais que influenciam o crescimento das algas, incluindo a concentração de fosfato, nitrato e sílica (dióxido de silício). Os resultados mostraram que os valores de fósforo total apresentaram aumento de 1,0, 0,9 e 0,8 mg/L, em janeiro, nos locais 2, 5 e 6, respectivamente. O valor mais alto do nitrato foi de 11,2 mg/L, em dezembro, no local 5, enquanto os menores valores de concentração foram em novembro (2,2 mg/L no local 6, e 3,7 mg/L no local 4). Além disso, a menor concentração de silicato foi de 0,4 mg/L, em novembro, no local 2, ao passo que a maior foi 2,4 mg/L, em junho de 2019, no local 6. Com base nos achados, é possível concluir que, durante o inverno, o nível da água aumentou devido às chuvas. Por esse motivo, as concentrações de nutrientes foram baixas durante o último período. Além disso, com o uso de mapas e técnicas de sensoriamento remoto, é possível determinar os valores esperados em torno da localização da estação como leituras preditivas futuras que compensam a dificuldade de alcançar essas áreas.

Palavras-chave: Concentração de NO_3 , PO_4 e SiO_2 , Algas Nutrientes, Técnicas de Sensoriamento Remoto, Pântanos Um El-Naaj, Qualidade da Água.

ABSTRACT

Epiphytic algae adherent to aquatic plants are an essential link in the composition of the food chain of any ecosystem. Epiphytic algae act as primary producers of the food chain in the aquatic ecosystem and as natural food for herbivorous zooplankton and fish. This study aimed to detect the presence of algae colonies through remote sensing and to analyze factors that affect the growth of algae through field survey and visual interpretation of satellite images in Lake Um El-Naaj. Samples were collected from six locations on Lake Um El-Naaj from November 2018 to June 2019. The algae samples were collected from submerged parts of emerging aquatic plants (aquatic macrophytes *Phragmites australis*) and stored in plastic bags with little ambient water and solutions for preservation in the field and the laboratory. Water samples were collected to study the nutritional factors that influence the growth of algae, including the concentration of Phosphate, Nitrate, and Silica (silicon dioxide). The results showed that the values of total phosphorus increased by 1.0, 0.9, and 0.8 mg/L, in January, in places 2, 5, and 6, respectively. The highest nitrate value was 11.2 mg/L in December at site 5, while the lowest concentration values were in November (2.2 mg/L at site 6 and 3.7 mg/L at site 4). Besides, the lowest

silicate concentration was 0.4 mg/L in November at site 2, while the highest was 2.4 mg/L in June 2019 at site 6. Based on the findings, it is possible to conclude that, during the winter, the water level increased due to the rain. For this reason, nutrient concentrations were low during the last period. Also, with the use of maps and remote sensing techniques, it is possible to determine the expected values around the station's location as future predictive readings that compensate for the difficulty of reaching these areas.

Keywords: NO_3 , PO_4 , and SiO_2 concentration, Nutrient Algae, Remote Sensing Techniques, Um El-Naaj Marshes, Water Quality.

المخلص

تعتبر الطحالب الملتصقة بالنباتات المائية حلقة مهمة في تكوين السلسلة الغذائية لأي نظام بيئي. تمثل الطحالب الملتصقة بالنباتات كمنتج رئيسي للسلسلة الغذائية في النظام البيئي المائي وكغذاء طبيعي للعوالق الحيوانية والأسماك العاشبية. هدفت هذه الدراسة للكشف عن وجود مستعمرات الطحالب وتحليل العوامل المؤثرة على نمو الطحالب من خلال المسح الميداني والتفسير المرئي لصور الأقمار الصناعية في بحيرة أم النعاج. تم جمع العينات من ستة مواقع في بحيرة أم النعاج من شهر تشرين الثاني 2018 إلى شهر حزيران 2019. جُمعت عينات الطحالب من الأجزاء الغاطسة للنباتات المائية من نبات الطحالب المائية الناشئة (القيصوب الأسترالي). جُمعت عينات النباتات في أكياس بلاستيكية مع القليل من الماء البيئي واستخدمت محاليل للمحافظة على الطحالب في الحقل والمختبر. تم جمع عينات المياه لدراسة العوامل الغذائية المؤثرة على نمو الطحالب منها تركيز الفوسفات والنترات والسيليكا (ثاني أكسيد السيليكون). أوضحت النتائج أن قيم الفوسفور الكلي أظهرت ارتفاع (1.0، 0.9، و 0.8) ملغم في شهر كانون الثاني في المواقع 2، 5، و 6 على التوالي. أعلى قيمة للنترات كانت تركيز 11.2 ملغم في شهر كانون الأول في الموقع 5، وأدنى قيمة نترات تركيز 2.2 ملغم في شهر تشرين الثاني في موقع 6 و 3.7 ملغم في الموقع 4. كما أن أدنى قيمة للسيليكا كانت 0.4 ملغم في شهر تشرين الثاني في موقع 2 وأعلى تركيز 2.4 ملغم في شهر حزيران من 2019 في الموقع 6. بناء على النتائج يمكن استنتاج ارتفاع مستوى الماء خلال فصل الشتاء بسبب الأمطار، لهذا السبب كانت تراكيز المغذيات منخفضة خلال الفترة الأخيرة، كما أن استخدام خرائط تقنيات الاستشعار عن بعد للتنبؤ بالقيم المتوقعة المحيطة بموقع المحطة كقرارات تنبؤية مستقبلية تُعوض عن صعوبة الوصول إلى هذه المناطق.

الكلمات المفتاحية: تركيز النترات، والفوسفات، السيليكا، مغذيات الطحالب، الاستشعار عن بعد، هور ام النعاج، نوعية المياه.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Epiphytic algae are found attached on surfaces of plants like mosses, other algae, and higher plants. Benthic algae require enough light for growth and suitable sites for connecting like submerged aquatic plants and emergent aquatic plants that found at the edge of the water body (Edward and David, 2010). Epiphytic algae play a vital role in the freshwater ecosystems because they are sources of primary production and an excellent nutrition source for the zooplankton (herbivores and for fish) (Graham *et al.*, 2009). Furthermore, they participate in sediment stabilization and regulation of the nutrients cycle (AL-Hassany and Hindi, 2016; AL Naqeeb *et al.*, 2020).

Epiphytic algae move the energy from the sediment to the water column (Salman *et al.*, 2013) and play a crucial function in the photosynthesis process transforming inorganic materials into organic ones. Also, it recycles nutrients and contributes to oxygen production via photosynthesis (Pouličková *et al.*, 2008). Phosphorus is a major ingredient that all organisms need, including algae, to build up nucleic acids (RNA and DNA), energy materials (ATP and ADP), and plasma membranes (Jarvis, 2000).

The importance of total phosphorus is due to the possibility of being used by aquatic organisms as a source of Phosphate after

conversion to inorganic phosphorus by the group of enzymes (Phosphatase), and dissolved total phosphorus is a determining factor for the growth of algae (McDowell and Sharpley, 2001).

Phosphorus often shows low concentrations in natural Waters. Algae are characterized by their ability to use the optimum concentration of phosphorus available for absorption and storage at concentrations beyond their need and more than what is found in the médium. This is called Luxury Uptake. Mixing from rain helps to release Phosphate from sediment, a source of water-soluble Phosphate. Nitrogen is a major component of algal growth and has an important role in cell division and some metabolic activities such as the building of fatty acids and proteins in algal cells (Boney, 1975). Fatty acids are the main source of Nitrogen in water, and its presence is associated with organic matter in water because it is a determinant of primary productivity in some environment (Ault *et al.*, 2000).

Silicon dioxide, SiO_2 , also known as Silica, is a major nutrient for the growth of diatoms in particular to build their structures (Reynolds, 1984). It is noted that the rate of dissolution of Silica has an essential role in regulating the pH as it acts as buffer solution Buffering Solution, and most natural water contains the element of Silica abundantly and available to diatoms in the basal water than acidic water (Wen and Chen, 2000; Hassan *et al.*, 2012). To study the growth of algae

and its effect on nutrients in the water surface.

A remote sensing program has been used. This progress has helped to achieve the accuracy in obtaining information from orthophoto imagery (aircraft, aerial photo, and satellite); it has become a basic science used to solve many issues related to land, atmosphere, surface phenomena and natural conditions without contact with any variances, through the amount of collection information provided and manipulation with digitization by high technology (Lillesand *et al.*, 2015; Hadi, and Mashee, 2017).

Sensing provides a unique method for obtaining land surface temperature (LST) information at the regional and global scale since most of the energy detected by the sensor in this spectral region is directly emitted by the land surface (Mashi, 2018).

The definitions interpolation process technique is making assumption areas that are closing to one another, which are corresponding to alike than those nearest apart, which led to clear predict values for any unmeasured regions, which influence those farther away. The inverse distance weighting (IDW) technique uses the values measured in observation stations to predict the expected values surrounding the station location as future predictive readings that compensate for the difficulty of reaching remote areas (Mitchel, 2005; Al Ramahi and Al Bahadly, 2017).

This study aimed to detect the presence of algae colonies that are environmentally friendly and community and analyze factors affecting algal traits through field survey and visual interpretation of satellite images and the use of statistical methods and theories.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

2.1. Study area

The study area in Maysan Province that in the south of Iraq located in Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) is in wright top 618607.7, 3632754.577 meter, and 770955.209, 3449601.505 meter in the left top. The Huwaizah marshes are located within the governorate of Maysan to the east of the Tigris River. The Huwaizah is bordered to the east and southeast by transnational area with Iran; to the south and southwest by the Basrah Governorates administer active boundary. The Huwaizah marshes represent the northeast corner of the property, with a total surface area of 90,691ha of primarily freshwater marsh.

The Huwaizah is the first national site that declared a Ramsar site for wetlands of international importance (Hassan *et al.*, 2012; Garstecki and Amr, 2011). Um El-Naaj lake, it is one of the most massive open water bodies partially dried during the marshes drying process in 1990. It is located in the northwest part of the Hawizeh marsh in Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) is in wright top 5294772.863, 3523084.449 meter, and 5308522.835, 3511666.143 meter in left bottom, covering an area of between 140 and 200 km² (Garstecki and Amr, 2011). Six sites were selected in Hor Al Huweiza Um El-Naaj lake identified by Ground Positioning System (GPS), (Table 1 and Figure 1).

The algae samples were collected from the submersible aquatic macrophyte plant (*Phragmites australis*) in plastic bags with little of the environment water. Formalin 4% was used for the preservation of algae in the field. Lugol's solution was also used to keep the original characteristics of the samples. Lugol was prepared by dissolving 20 g of Potassium Iodide in 200 ml of distilled water. After, 10 g of Iodine crystals were added; then, glacial acetic acid was added to the mixture, and this solution was preserved in a dark bottle and used by a proportion of 1% (1mL of the solution to every 100 mL of the sample that contains algae) (Prescott, 1964).

2.2. Epiphytic Algae Colony

Epiphytic algae attached to plants or to artificial surfaces contribute to taking the phytonutrients present from the water column in the growing season, as they have a role in removing 80% of ammonium, 15% of nitrates and 70% of the adequate soluble phosphorus entering the water surface within 15 days of exposure to these plant nutrients as these high removal rates increase the growth of adherent Epiphytic algae and then use it to treat water-rich in plant nutrients.

The rate of taking phosphorous by adherent Epiphytic algae ranges from 1-3 mg phosphorous/m² of wetland area per week, so many of these algae are essential consumers of phosphorus from the water column. Therefore algae is vital evidence of the availability of plant nutrients and pollution as well as being a candidate for materials Water suspended solid (Morgan and Kitting, 1984; Cronk and Mitsch, 1994; Dere *et al.*, 2002).

Given the great environmental importance of algae, as it is an important factor in determining the nutritional level of any ecosystem, this has led to the researchers' interest in studying it

qualitatively and quantitatively (Figure 2).

2.3. Total Nitrogen ($\mu\text{g/L}$)

The total Nitrogen in the sample was converted to Nitrate in the digestion method with potassium persulphate. According to Rice *et al.*, 2012; Salman *et al.*, 2017, 25 mL of the sample were put in an autoclave 121°C for 30 minutes after the addition of 0.3 g of potassium persulphate; then, it was cooled to the room temperature and pH regulated with NaOH and HCl solution to reach 7 - 9; later, the volume was completed to 100 mL with NH_4Cl -EDTA concentrate solution. After that, the sample passed through the Cadmium column, and the given sample gathered after neglecting the first 25 mL. The first reagent Sulphanilamide has been added, and the sample was put in the darkness for 4 - 6 minutes. The second reagent, naphthyl ethylenediamine-dihydrochloride, has been added, and, finally, after 10 - 12 minutes, the absorption has been measured by the spectrophotometer on wavy length 543 nanometers.

2.4. Total Phosphate (mg/L)

The total Phosphate was measured by the method of absorption (Rice *et al.*, 2012; Parsons *et al.*, 1984). A total of 100 mL of the sample was put in the autoclave 121°C after the addition of 5 mL of sulphuric acid 1N and 0.7 g of potassium persulphate. Then, it was cooled to the room temperature and treated with 10 mL of the reduced solution composed of ascorbic acid, antimony potassium tartrate, ammonium molybdate, and diluted sulphuric acid. The color was changed to blue. Finally, the absorption was measured by the spectrophotometer on 885-nanometer wavy length.

2.5. Reactive Silicate (Silicon Dioxide SiO_2 , $\mu\text{g/L}$)

The reactive silicate was measured according to the method described by Rice *et al.*, 2012; Salman *et al.*, 2017; and Parsons *et al.*, 1984. A total of 25 mL of the sample was taken. Another 10 mL of ammonium molybdate was added. Then, the flask was shaken. After 10 minutes, 15 mL of the reduced solution (sulfide, oxalic acid, and sulphuric acid) was added. The sample was then left 2-3 hours until the blue color stabilizes. Finally, the absorption was measured by the spectrophotometer on the 810-nanometer wavy length.

2.6. Remote Sensing (RS) Processing

Data of remote sensing techniques used in this study included three Imaginary, three periods of time, Landsat-8 OLI images Shaped and rectangular dimensions path: 167 km and row: 38 km. These data were acquired on the 22nd November 2018, 24th December 2018, and 20th January 2019. These periods matched with the timing of fieldwork data collection. The images were downloaded from the United States Geological Survey (USGS, 2017; Al-Ramahi, 2020).

The Landsat images were first converted to Top-of-Atmosphere (TOA) radiance using radiometric calibration coefficients in the metadata file. ArcGIS 10.5 is the digital image processing software used to process the Landsat 8 IMAGES. Twenty-six ground control points (GCPs) were selected from the images and rectified to the UTM (Universal Transverse Mercator). World Geodetic System 1984 (WGS 84) projection using coordinates obtained from Global Positioning System (GPS), (20). For the spatial interpolation of the geometric correction, the image's original digital numbers (DNs) were preserved by subsequently using a Bilinear resampling method. After geometric correction, the images were atmospherically corrected. The atmosphere may potentially affect image by absorbing, scattering, and refracting light.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

3.1. Analysis of Factors Affecting Algal Trait (NO_3 , PO_4 , SiO_2)

The samples were analyzed in the laboratory and extracted the values of (NO_3 , PO_4 , SiO_2). The data was tabulated to explain it in Geographic Information Systems (GIS) programs, which is the best application program to simulate spatial data with remote sensing techniques, and through Landsat 8 satellite imagery.

3.2. Spatial Analysis

The spatial analysis of these samples and the simulation of the study area maps were made, aiming to know the effect of these factors on the water quality and algae present in this region. Moreover, it was intended to know the unknown areas in which it is difficult to obtain data (the prediction process). Through these six stations, data is not sufficient to cover the study area. Through the application of theories and statistical

methods used in geographic information systems (GIS) (Al Ramahi, and Al Bahadly, 2020), it was possible to know and cover the study area of Um El-Naaj lake in Al-Hweizeh marsh (Table 2).

3.3. Factors Affecting (PO₄) Analysis

Phosphorus is an important nutrient, representing an intermediate component of energy metabolism (Schulze *et al.*, 2005). Phosphorus is found in many forms and may be present in the soluble or pigmented form. The pigmented way is found mainly in algae and aquatic plants (Smith, 2004). The dissolved form is found in various forms such as Orthophosphate, Polyphosphate, and the Orthophosphate may be rapidly represented by living organisms, in natural water (Wetzel and Likens, 2013). The concentration of total phosphorus raised 1.0, 0.9, and 0.8 mg/L, in January, at sites 2, 5, and 6, respectively (Table 2). The lowest concentration was found in November and December on all sites. The results of phosphorus concentrations showed a significant increase that may be a result of high water levels or rainfall that washed off phosphorus compounds from soil to the river when washing agricultural land fertilized with phosphate fertilizers (Sims and Sharpley, 2005). The high concentration of Phosphate leads to the dense growth of algae, which in turn reduces light transmittance and dissolved oxygen concentrations, resulting in slow decomposition of organic matter and nutrient recycling (McDowell and Sharpley, 2001; Adamus, 2001). On the other hand, low concentrations may be explained by the consumption of Phosphate by algae and aquatic plants (Kassim and Al-Saadi 1995) (Figures 3 and 4).

3.4. Factors Affecting (NO₃) Analysis

The Nitrate is the predominant form of inorganic Nitrogen in the aquatic environment (Smith, 2004), and the variation in nitrogen compounds is due to increased human activity in agriculture and industry and the resulting residues of a container on nitrogen compounds (Johnson, 2004). The results showed that the lowest nitrate concentrations were 2.2 mg/L in November at site 6, and 3.7 mg/L in the same month, but site 5. In December, the highest concentration was 11.2 mg/L (Table 2).

The high concentration of nitrates is due to the washing of the land adjacent to the river and the erosion of the soil containing nitrogen compounds from the animal residues (Al-Nimma, 1982). The decrease in Nitrate may be due to its

consumption of revival, which is the primary source of plants in general and algae in particular (Saad and Antoine 1978) (Figure 5).

3.5. Factors Affecting (SiO₂) Analysis

Silicates are widely found in Iraqi waters, and they are of great importance for diatoms as they are needed for the building of their siliceous skeletons (Goldman and Horne, 1983). Its concentration ranges from 1-10 mg.L⁻¹ in natural water. The concentration of Silica between 0.5-0.8 mg.L⁻¹ is determinant for the growth of diatoms (Reid, 1961). It plays a vital role in increasing the number of diatoms and the length of their survival (Chatterjee, 2014). High concentrations of silicate characterize Iraq waters. This is due to the geological nature of land in which Tigris and Euphrates Rivers flow. The results showed the lowest concentration of silicate was 0.4 mg/L, in November, at site 2; The highest concentration was 2.4 mg/L in June 2019 at site 6, and there were no significant spatial differences among the study sites. In general, the active silicate concentrations in the studied area exceeded the need for phytoplankton. This phenomenon is known in Iraqi waters, which have high concentrations of active silicates. The concentrations of silicates obtained are not consistent with the study of (AL-Saeedy, 2014; AL-Hassany and Hindi, 2016), shown in Figure 6.

4. CONCLUSIONS:

The samples were analyzed in the laboratory and extracted the values of NO₃, PO₄, SiO₂. The data was tabulated to analyze in Geographic Information Systems (GIS) programs. The nutrient values ranged from 0.01 - 1 mg/L for PO₄; 2.2 - 11.2 mg/L for NO₃; and 0.4 - 2.44 mg/L for SiO₂. Also, it can be concluded that, during the winter, the water level was increased due to rainfall; that is, the nutrients concentrations were low during the last period.

The Sample concentrations were useful in determining the acceptable water quality, which helped in the presence of a great diversity of some species in the marshes (Um El-Naaj lake). By using remote sensing techniques, maps were produced to predict the expected values surrounding the station's location as future predictive readings that compensate for the difficulty in reaching these areas.

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Table 1. The station Location Names and global coordinate system (λ , φ) converted to Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) coordinate (x , y).

Stations (ST)	Stations Name (E)	Latitude Degree (λ)	Longitude Degree (φ)	x-axis coordinate (UTM)	y-axis coordinate (UTM)
1	Um bzazen	31.617211	47.603245	746945	3500950
2	AboAthba 1	31.644485	47.636462	750024	3504050
3	AboAthba 2	31.634116	47.636401	750046	3502900
4	Alkhabta	31.617198	47.570533	743841	3500870
5	Aboliefafa 1	31.611951	47.670161	753309	3500520
6	Aboliefafa 2	31.586911	47.673059	753652	3497750

Table 2. The concentration of NO_3 , PO_4 , and SiO_2 according to the station and month of analysis.

Station	November			December			January		
	NO_3 ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	PO_4 (mg/L)	SiO_2 ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	NO_3 ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	PO_4 (mg/L)	SiO_2 ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	NO_3 ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	PO_4 (mg/L)	SiO_2 ($\mu\text{g/L}$)
St1	4	0.035	0.666	4.23	0.048	0.666	3.33	0.432	1.67
St2	5.12	0.069	0.45	6.21	0.79	0.475	4.97	0.839	1.01
St3	6.5	0.051	0.625	6.62	0.067	0.725	4.88	0.72	0.68
St4	3.72	0.032	0.642	4.29	0.011	0.681	3.77	0.627	0.98
St5	5.32	0.014	0.663	11.2	0.121	0.71	7.2	0.917	1.5
St6	2.2	0.012	0.567	8.72	0.181	0.7	8.31	1.02	2.44

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 1. (a) represents Iraq Administrator; (b) the satellite Landsat imagery; (c) Study Area Site in Maysan city; and (d) Observation station name in study area Um El-Naaj lake including the six stations. Note: The study was conducted during three months, from November 2018- January 2019.

Figure 2. Types of Epiphytic algae affixed to aquatic plants in one of the station sites, which contribute to the ecosystem and a major nutrient.

Figure 3. Study Area. The satellite Landsat imagery 8 is representing composite bands (4, 3, 2); The form shapefile (polygon) simulated study area as Um El-Naaj lake Station site.

Figure 4. Factors Affecting Phosphorus (PO_4) Analysis, applied Interpolation and contour line techniques for all six observation stations in November, December, and January and remarked the PO_4 values.

Figure 5. Factors Affecting Nitrate (NO_3) Analysis, applied Interpolation and contour line techniques for all six observation stations in November, December, and January and remarked the NO_3 values.

Figure 6. Factors Affecting Silica (SiO_2) Analysis, applied Interpolation and contour line techniques for all six observation stations in November, December, and January and remarked the Si values.